

LANGUAGE SKILLS OF THE KINDERGARTEN LEARNERS DURING THE NEW NORMAL

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Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners during the New Normal

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of the "new normal" on the language development of kindergarten learners, as schools adapted to changes in teaching and learning environments. The research focuses on understanding how these shifts have affected language proficiency at Magsaysay Elementary School and King of Zion Christian Learning Center, Inc. The objective serves as the basis for the language skills development plan which includes assessing the proficiency levels in expressive and receptive skills among kindergarten learners, as well as identifying factors that may influence language development in the new normal setting. The study employs a descriptive-comparative research design to analyze the language proficiency of kindergarten learners during the new normal. The research is conducted in kindergarten classrooms at Magsaysay Elementary School, Sevilla District, Bohol Division and King of Zion Christian Learning Center, Inc., Cebu Province Division. The respondents of this study were 13 kindergarten teachers and 47 selected parents. The research instrument was researcher-made survey questionnaire designed for both parents and teachers respectively to be utilized in order to gather ample data relative to the study focusing on language skills of the kindergarten learners. Statistical treatment involves frequency count, simple percentage, weighted mean, and T-test for independent samples to analyze and compare data. The results of the study show that most parents think their kids have excellent linguistic abilities. Furthermore, the majority of teacher perceptions were shown to be proficient. According to the study's findings, teachers must focus on these elements since doing so will help students' language proficiency. In order to improve the language activities for the learners, it is necessary to use a variety of tactics, engaging activities, and building on their prior knowledge. Thus, a plan for developing language skills is advised.

Keywords: *early childhood education, language skills, kindergarten learners, descriptive-comparative research*

Introduction

Early Childhood Education (ECE) is widely recognized as a cornerstone of a child's holistic development, laying the foundation for their future academic and social success. In the Philippines, the Universal Kindergarten Implementation, launched in the 2011-2012 school year, marked a significant step towards ensuring that all five-year-old children have access to quality early education. This initiative aimed to foster their development in essential areas such as communication, socialization, and foundational literacy skills, preparing them for the transition to primary school.

However, the COVID-19 pandemic brought about unprecedented disruptions to educational systems worldwide, forcing a shift towards alternative learning modalities. In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented blended modular learning, a hybrid approach combining online and offline learning activities, to ensure the continuity of education during lockdowns and restrictions. While this approach offered flexibility and accessibility, concerns arose regarding its potential impact on the language development of young learners, particularly those in kindergarten.

Previous research has shed light on the potential challenges of distance learning for language acquisition. Studies by Wei et al. (2021) and Bao et al. (2020) have underscored the potential discrepancy between verbal and written language skills in young children during periods of remote learning. While technology may have facilitated oral communication and interaction, it may have inadvertently hindered the development of written language proficiency, including spelling, grammar, and written expression. These findings suggest that the transition to blended learning modalities could have unintended consequences for the language skills of kindergarten learners.

Despite the growing body of research on the impact of blended learning on language development, a critical gap remains in understanding the perceptions of parents and teachers regarding kindergarten learners' language abilities within this context. Existing studies have primarily focused on the learners themselves, neglecting the valuable insights of those directly involved in their education. Parents, as primary caregivers and educators, play a pivotal role in fostering their children's language development, while teachers are responsible for guiding and supporting their students' linguistic growth in formal learning environments. Their perspectives, shaped by their unique experiences and observations, offer a rich source of information that can illuminate the challenges and opportunities presented by blended modular learning.

This study aims to bridge this gap by investigating the perceptions of parents and teachers regarding kindergarten learners' language skills during blended modular learning, considering their individual profiles and experiences. By analyzing these perceptions, the study seeks to identify potential factors influencing language development, including the role of technology, family support, and classroom practices. This research will contribute to a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between blended learning, language development, and the perspectives of key stakeholders in the educational process. Ultimately, the findings of this study will provide valuable insights for developing effective strategies to support and enhance the language skills of kindergarten learners in the "new normal" of education, ensuring that all children have the opportunity to reach their full potential.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the language skills of the kindergarten learners during the new normal at Magsaysay Elementary School in Bohol Division and King of Zion Christian Learning Center Inc. in Cebu Province Division for school year 2022-2023 as basis for language skills development plans. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Parent-respondents; and
 - 1.1.1. age and gender;
 - 1.1.2. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.1.3. number of children; and
 - 1.1.4. combined family monthly income?
 - 1.2. Teacher-respondents?
 - 1.2.1. age and gender;
 - 1.2.2. highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.2.3. length of service?
2. What is the level of language skills of the kindergarten learners during blended modular learning as perceived by the respondent-groups in terms of:
 - 2.1. receptive language; and
 - 2.2. expressive language?
3. Is there a significant difference between the parents and teachers' perception on the language skills of the kindergarten learners during blended modular learning?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what language skills development plans can be proposed?

Literature Review

The COVID-19 pandemic has irrevocably altered the landscape of education, particularly for young learners. The abrupt transition to remote and hybrid learning models has presented unprecedented challenges, impacting various aspects of children's development, including their language skills. This comprehensive review investigates the complex interplay between the new normal and the language acquisition journey of kindergarten learners, exploring both the challenges and opportunities that have emerged.

The Impact of the New Normal on Language Development

The shift to remote learning has significantly disrupted the traditional learning environment, creating a unique set of challenges for kindergarten learners' language development.

Reduced Face-to-Face Interaction: A Foundation for Language Acquisition. The cornerstone of language development lies in social interaction. Face-to-face communication provides opportunities for spontaneous conversations, observation of social cues, and practice of speaking and listening skills with peers and teachers (Zhou, 2021; Marini et al., 2021). The absence of this crucial element in remote learning environments has had a profound impact on kindergarten learners' ability to develop their linguistic skills.

Limited Exposure to Rich Language Input: The Importance of Language-Rich Environments. Kindergarten learners thrive in language-rich environments where they are exposed to a diverse range of vocabulary, grammatical structures, and conversational styles. Physical classrooms, with their vibrant interactions, shared reading experiences, and opportunities for storytelling, provide a rich tapestry of language input (O'Brien et al., 2020). Remote learning environments, while offering some opportunities, often lack the same depth and richness of language exposure, potentially hindering vocabulary development and overall language growth.

Navigating the Digital Divide: Challenges of Adapting to Online Platforms. Young learners are often unfamiliar with the intricacies of online platforms, requiring them to navigate new technological tools, engage in virtual discussions, and express themselves effectively through digital mediums (Farris & Mohamed, 2022). This digital divide can create a barrier to effective communication and limit their ability to fully participate in online learning experiences.

The Power of Oral Language Practice: The Missing Link in Remote Learning. Oral language practice is essential for developing fluency, pronunciation, and comprehension skills. The lack of face-to-face interactions and reduced opportunities for oral language practice in remote learning environments can hinder the development of kindergarten learners' speaking and listening skills (Farris & Mohamed, 2022).

Beyond the Screen: The Importance of Physical Books and Writing Activities. Physical books provide tactile experiences, allowing learners to explore the physicality of words and engage in shared reading experiences. Hands-on writing activities, such as drawing, tracing, and writing letters, are essential for developing fine motor skills and early literacy skills (Kasilveloo et al., 2022). The shift to remote learning has often limited access to these essential resources, potentially impacting emergent reading skills, letter recognition, and writing proficiency.

Finding the Balance: The Overreliance on Digital Resources and the Need for Print-Based Materials. While digital resources offer

valuable learning opportunities, an overreliance on technology can disrupt the balance between digital and print-based materials, potentially hindering the development of essential language skills (Giannakopoulou, 2021). A balanced approach that incorporates both digital and print-based materials is crucial for fostering comprehensive language development.

The Power of Peer Interaction: The Social Fabric of Language Development. Peer interactions are essential for language development, as children learn from each other through conversation, collaboration, and play (Sun, Toh, & Steinkrauss, 2020). The absence of face-to-face peer interactions in remote learning environments can impact language growth and the development of social communication skills.

Bridging the Gap: Parental Involvement and the Importance of Equitable Support. Parental involvement has become crucial in supporting language development during the new normal, but not all parents have the resources or knowledge to provide optimal language support (Luo et al., 2023; Karpava, 2021). Efforts to bridge this gap and ensure equitable access to language-rich learning opportunities for all kindergarten learners are essential.

The Pandemic's Shadow: Emotional and Psychological Effects on Language Development. The pandemic and associated disruptions have had emotional and psychological effects on kindergarten learners, which can indirectly impact language development (Washington-Nortey et al., 2022). Feelings of stress, anxiety, or isolation can affect children's engagement, motivation, and language use. Creating a supportive and nurturing environment, both in virtual and physical settings, is crucial for promoting healthy language development.

Understanding the Foundations of Language Acquisition

The study draws upon three prominent theoretical frameworks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the development of language skills in kindergarten learners:

Behavioral Theory: Learning Through Imitation and Reinforcement. This theory emphasizes the role of environment and conditioning in shaping language behaviors (Aizenberg, 2022). Children learn language through imitation and reinforcement from adults, with parents and caregivers serving as the primary language models.

Nativistic Theory: The Innate Capacity for Language. This theory suggests that children have an innate ability to learn language, with a biological predisposition for language acquisition (Johnslov, 2018). The human brain is equipped with a Language Acquisition Device (LAD), which enables children to acquire language rapidly and effortlessly.

Constructivist Learning Theory: Active Learners Constructing Knowledge. This theory emphasizes the active role of learners in constructing knowledge based on their existing understanding (Obi, Nja Cecilia, Ukpepi, Cornelius, & Ndifon, Rita A., 2019). Children learn language by interacting with their environment, exploring their surroundings, and constructing their own understanding of language.

Policy and Program Support: Government Initiatives to Foster Language Development

The Philippine government has implemented several policies and programs to support kindergarten education and language development, recognizing the crucial role of early language acquisition in a child's educational journey:

Kindergarten Education Act (RA 10157): Making Kindergarten Mandatory. This law mandates kindergarten as the first stage of compulsory and mandatory formal education, highlighting the importance of early childhood education in laying the foundation for future learning.

Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (RA 10533): Investing in Kindergarten Education. This law emphasizes the significance of kindergarten teaching as a strong arm to eradicate poverty and achieve economic stability, recognizing the link between early education and social and economic progress.

DepEd Order No. 18 s. 2017: Supporting the Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy Program. This order provides guidelines on the utilization of funds for the Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy Program, a crucial initiative aimed at enhancing the reading and numeracy skills of young learners.

DepEd Order No. 47, s. 2016: The Omnibus Policy on Kindergarten Education. This order outlines the comprehensive policy framework for kindergarten education, ensuring a standardized approach to early childhood education across the country.

DepEd Order 28, s. 2013: Promoting Mother Tongue Based-Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE). This order provides guidelines on the implementation of the Mother Tongue Based-Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE), recognizing the importance of incorporating the learner's mother tongue in the early learning process.

Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy Program (ELLN): Building a Foundation for Literacy. This program seeks to improve the reading and numeracy skills of learners from kindergarten to Grade 3, equipping teachers with the necessary tools and resources to foster language and literacy development.

Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI): Assessing Reading Proficiency: This assessment tool measures the reading

proficiency of students, providing valuable data to inform interventions and support struggling learners.

Moving Forward in the New Normal:

The COVID-19 pandemic has presented significant challenges to the language development of kindergarten learners. The shift to remote and hybrid learning models has disrupted traditional learning environments, creating a unique set of obstacles for young learners. However, the government's policies and programs, along with the dedicated efforts of educators, parents, and caregivers, can help mitigate these challenges and foster language development during the new normal.

It is crucial to provide targeted support, create language-rich environments, and address existing educational disparities to ensure equitable access to language-rich learning opportunities for all kindergarten learners. By embracing a holistic approach that addresses the unique needs of young learners in the new normal, we can empower them to thrive in their language acquisition journey and lay a

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a descriptive comparative research design to investigate and compare perceptions of kindergarten learners' language skills during the "new normal." The study utilizes a survey methodology to gather data from two key groups: parents and teachers. The research aims to explore significant differences in perceptions between these groups, analyze respondent profiles (age, gender, educational background), and provide a comprehensive comparison of attitudes, beliefs, and routines related to language development. To ensure the validity of the survey instruments, the questionnaires were reviewed by experts, including education program supervisors in kindergarten and public schools district supervisors. These experts were provided with cover letters outlining the research study's purpose, its premises, and the criteria for the respondents. This review process aimed to ensure the content validity of the survey instruments.

Respondents

This study focuses on the kindergarten teachers and parents of kindergarten learners from two schools: Magsaysay Elementary School in Bohol and King of Zion Christian Learning Center, Inc. in Cebu. The respondents include 5 teachers and 18 parents from Magsaysay Elementary School, and 8 teachers and 29 parents from King of Zion Christian Learning Center, resulting in a total of 60 participants. The study uses universal sampling for teachers and simple random sampling for parents. The selection of respondents was based on their availability and relevance to the study's focus on blended learning and language skills development during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Instrument

A researcher-made survey questionnaire was developed for both parents and teachers to collect data on the language skills of kindergarten learners during blended-modular learning. The questionnaire was divided into three main sections. The first part focused on demographic profiling of the respondents. For parents, questions addressed age, gender, highest educational attainment, number of children, and combined monthly income, while for teachers, it included age, gender, years of service, and highest educational attainment.

The second section of the survey comprised a checklist evaluating the language skills of kindergarten learners during blended-modular distance learning.

To ensure the validity of the instrument, the survey was reviewed and validated by experts, including a Kindergarten Education Program Supervisor and Public School District Supervisors. Cover letters detailing the study's purpose, respondent criteria, and the research objectives were provided to each expert for feedback and validation.

Procedure

After obtaining approval for the research title and conducting a literature review, the researcher prepared a survey questionnaire to assess kindergarten learners' language skills. Permissions were secured from the Schools Division of Bohol and Cebu, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents.

Data collection took place over three weeks during meetings organized by the Homeroom Parents-Teachers Association (HRPTA), where parents completed the questionnaires with assistance from the researcher. Following this period, responses were tallied, and data analysis commenced.

Confidentiality was prioritized, ensuring that results would be kept secure and available only for educational reference. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed about the study's purpose. The study complied with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, implementing measures to protect personal data and uphold ethical research standards.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher obtained written permission from the principal to conduct the study and collect qualitative data on school premises.

This initial approval ensured that the research adhered to institutional guidelines. Informed consent was then presented to all respondents, ensuring they fully understood the purpose of the study, their rights, and the implications of their participation. This process emphasized the protection of respondents' confidentiality and the safeguarding of their identities.

To facilitate a comfortable environment for the participants, the researchers allotted sufficient time for them to complete the questionnaires. They provided guidance on the questions and how to answer the survey accurately, ensuring clarity and comprehension. This approach was designed to respect the respondents' autonomy and encourage honest and thoughtful responses.

After the completion of the questionnaires, the researcher promptly collected and tabulated the data, ensuring the secure handling of all information gathered. Throughout the study, the researcher maintained ethical standards by prioritizing participants' rights, confidentiality, and well-being, thus fostering a respectful and supportive research environment.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, explains, and conducts an analysis of the information obtained from the respondents. This includes the tabulated data for the respondent profiles, the language proficiency level of kindergarten learners and the significant difference between parents' and teachers' perception on the language skills of the kindergarten learners during new normal.

Profile of the Respondents

This section outlines the profiles of respondents at Magsaysay Elementary School, including parents and teachers. Key factors for parents include age, gender, education, number of children, and family income, while for teachers, the focus is on age, gender, education, and length of service. These demographics are vital for understanding their impact on the educational context.

Parent-Respondents

Age and Gender

Table 1 indicates the age and gender of the parent-respondents.

Table 1. *Age and Gender of the Parent-Respondents*

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
50-59	1	5.56	0	0.00	1	5.56
40-49	7	38.89	1	5.56	8	44.44
30-39	5	27.78	0	0.00	5	27.78
20-29	4	22.22	0	0.00	4	22.22
Total	17	94.44	1	5.56	18	100.00

The data shows that the majority of parent-respondents are aged 40-49, accounting for 44.44%, and most are female (94.44%). A smaller portion is aged 30-39 (27.78%) and 20-29 (22.22%), with only 5.56% aged 50 or older. The results suggest that most kindergarten parents are younger and predominantly female.

The findings align with research by Barratt-Pugh et al. (2022), which suggests that younger parents may have better access to early childhood education resources and are more likely to prioritize kindergarten education, often being in the workforce and able to afford the cost.

Highest Educational Attainment

Table 2 displays the parents' highest level of education.

Table 2. *Highest Educational Attainment of the Parent-Respondents*

Educational Attainment	f	%
College Level	1	5.56
High School Graduate	6	33.33
High School Level	3	16.67
Elementary Graduate	5	27.78
Elementary Level	3	16.67
Total	18	100.00

The data shows that the majority of parent-respondents are high school graduates (33.33%), followed by elementary graduates (27.78%). A smaller portion attended college (5.56%) or have not completed high school or elementary education. The results indicate that most parents have limited access to higher education.

This educational background may negatively impact their ability to provide academic support to their children, potentially contributing to broader educational disparities. As noted by Vasiljevic-Prodanovic et al. (2023), parents with higher education levels tend to access

better resources and opportunities for their children, enhancing early childhood cognitive and language development.

Number of Children

Table 3 lists the total number of children raised by parents of learners attending Magsaysay Elementary School.

Table 3. Parent-Respondents' Number of Children

<i>Number of Children</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
More than 4	6	33.33
3-4	5	27.78
1-2	7	38.89
Total	18	100.00

The data indicates that 38.89% of parent-respondents have 1-2 children, 33.33% have more than four, and 27.78% have 3-4 children, suggesting a trend toward smaller families. This pattern may be influenced by factors such as income, education, and regional considerations. According to Alenezi et al. (2023), having siblings can enhance social development for kindergarten learners by fostering skills like sharing and conflict resolution. However, it's important to note that family size alone does not determine a child's social skills; parenting style and exposure to diverse environments also significantly influence development.

Combined Family Monthly Income

The table below provides information on the combined family income, in Philippine Pesos, of parents from Magsaysay Elementary School.

Table 4. Parent-Respondents' Combined Family Monthly Income

<i>Monthly Income (in pesos)</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
15,001-20,000	1	5.56
10,001-15,000	1	5.56
10,000 and below	16	88.89
Total	18	100.00

Table 4 illustrates the combined monthly income of parents at Magsaysay Elementary School. It reveals that a significant majority, 88.89% (16 families), have a monthly income of P10,000 or less. This suggests that most families are struggling financially, indicating a high cost of living and the need for increased incomes or reduced expenses to improve their financial situation. Cohen and Anders (2020) note that socio-economic inequality often results in wealth concentration among a small segment of the population, impacting the majority with lower incomes due to systemic factors and economic structures.

Teacher-Respondents

Age and Gender

This table shows the ages and genders of the five teachers of Magsaysay Elementary School.

Table 5. Age and Gender of the Teacher-Respondents

<i>Age (in years)</i>	<i>Female</i>		<i>Male</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
40-49	3	60.00	0	0.00	3	60.00
30-39	2	40.00	0	0.00	2	40.00
Total	5	100.00	0	0.00	5	100.00

Table 5 shows that 60% of teacher-respondents are aged 40-49, while 40% are 30-39. All respondents are female, highlighting a lack of gender diversity, with no male teachers represented. The findings suggest a need for more diverse representation in the teaching staff, particularly in terms of gender and age.

According to Korosidou et al. (2021), the predominance of female teachers can be attributed to societal expectations and historical trends within the profession. The current age distribution may reflect generational preferences in career choices related to teaching.

Highest Educational Attainment

Table 6 displays the highest level of education attained by a teacher from Magsaysay Elementary School.

Table 6. Teacher-Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Master's Graduate	1	20.00
With Master's Units	4	80.00
Total	5	100.00

Table 6 shows that 80% of teacher-respondents at Magsaysay Elementary School have completed Master's units, while 20% hold Master's degrees. This indicates that most teachers are pursuing advanced education to enhance their skills and knowledge as part of their professional development.

According to Albaiz and Ernest (2021), pursuing a Master's program allows teachers to specialize in specific subjects or fields, improving their teaching capabilities and preparing them for leadership roles. This trend reflects a growing commitment to higher education among educators.

Length of Service

The table below details the length of service of Magsaysay Elementary School's teachers.

Table 7. Length of Service of Teacher-Respondents

<i>Length of Service (in years)</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
16 and above	3	60.00
11-15	0	0.00
6-10	1	20.00
1-5	1	20.00
Total	5	100.00

Table 7 reveals that 60% of teacher-respondents have 16 years or more of service, while 20% have 6-10 years and another 20% have 1-5 years. The results indicate that the majority of teachers at Magsaysay Elementary School possess significant teaching experience, suggesting that experienced educators are likely to be more effective in enhancing student performance.

According to Yang et al. (2022), a length of service of 16 years or more reflects stability in the teaching profession, suggesting that established teachers are more inclined to remain in the field.

Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as Perceived by the Parents and Teachers during the New Normal

Receptive language is the ability to understand spoken and written language, crucial for communication and learning in kindergarten. The transition to mixed modular learning underscores the need for parental and teacher support in language development. The table shows assessments of children's receptive language skills, focusing on their comprehension and interaction with educational resources.

Table 8. Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Receptive Language as perceived by Parents

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1	Points to family member when asked to do so	3.17	Proficient
2	Points to 5 body parts on himself when asked to do so	3.28	Advanced
3	Points to 5 named pictured objects when asked to do so	3.17	Proficient
4	Follows one-step instructions that include simple prepositions (e.g., in, on, under, etc.)	3.28	Advanced
5	Follows 2-step instructions that include simple prepositions	3.11	Proficient
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.20	Proficient

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50-3.24- Proficient ;1.75 - 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 - 1.74- Beginning

Table 8 shows parents' perceptions of kindergarten learners' language skills during blended modular learning. Parents generally view their children as proficient in most areas, except in specific tasks related to naming objects and following step-by-step instructions. Engaging activities like reading, storytelling, and word games help children expand their vocabulary and build confidence in their communication skills, creating a supportive environment for language development.

Stites et al. (2021) found that students with receptive language difficulties are often unprepared for classroom challenges. Teachers' discourse, reading instruction, and post-reading activities significantly support the growth of children's receptive vocabulary.

Table 9. Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Receptive Language as perceived by Teachers

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1	Points to family member when asked to do so	3.60	Advanced
2	Points to 5 body parts on himself when asked to do so	3.80	Advanced
3	Points to 5 named pictured objects when asked to do so	3.60	Advanced
4	Follows one-step instructions that include simple prepositions (e.g., in, on, under, etc.)	3.40	Advanced
5	Follows 2-step instructions that include simple prepositions	3.20	Proficient
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.52	Advanced

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50-3.24- Proficient ;1.75 - 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 - 1.74- Beginning

Table 9 indicates that teachers perceive kindergarten learners to have advanced receptive language skills, with the exception of one item. Teachers believe that these skills enable children to participate in class activities, follow instructions, and understand lessons. However, difficulties in receptive language can impact listening, attention, behavior, and social skills. Teachers employ various activities to support learners facing challenges, emphasizing that understanding spoken and written language is crucial for their overall development.

Liebig et al. (2021) note that when children struggle to understand language, it can lead to confusion and frustration, sometimes causing them to act out. Providing activities that enhance language comprehension helps build their confidence in receptive language skills.

Table 10. Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Expressive Language as perceived by Parents

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Uses 5-20 recognizable words	3.17	Proficient
2	Uses pronouns (e.g., I, me, ako, akin)	3.39	Advanced
3	Uses 2-3 words verb-noun combinations (e.g., hingi gatas)	3.28	Advanced
4	Names objects in pictures	3.28	Advanced
5	Speaks in grammatically correct 2-3-word sentences	3.06	Proficient
6	Asks "what" questions	3.33	Advanced
7	Asks "who" and "why" questions	3.17	Proficient
8	Gives account of recent experiences (with prompting) in order of occurrence using past tense	3.22	Proficient
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.24	Proficient

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50- 3.24- Proficient ;1.75 – 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 – 1.74– Beginning

Table 10 highlights parents' perceptions of kindergarten learners' expressive language skills. Results indicate that parents see their children as proficient in using up to 20 recognizable words, forming grammatically correct sentences, and asking questions like "who" and "why." Additionally, learners demonstrate advanced skills in fluency, emotional expression, and open-ended questioning. Parents support this development through reading, singing, and engaging in conversations, which enriches vocabulary and communication skills. Such language experiences are crucial for fostering meaningful interactions and comprehension.

Liao et al. (2021) emphasize that enhancing students' communication skills is crucial in education, particularly in primary classrooms where expressive language is essential for learning across subjects. Teachers often assess a child's overall development through their expressive language abilities, which reflect the quality of language support provided. Research indicates that developing expressive language skills is more closely linked to improved reading outcomes than receptive skills, highlighting their importance in early education.

Table 11. Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Expressive Language as perceived by Teachers

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Uses 5-20 recognizable words	2.80	Proficient
2	Uses pronouns (e.g., I, me, ako, akin)	3.20	Proficient
3	Uses 2-3 words verb-noun combinations (e.g., hingi gatas)	3.20	Proficient
4	Names objects in pictures	3.80	Advanced
5	Speaks in grammatically correct 2-3-word sentences	3.00	Proficient
6	Asks "what" questions	3.80	Advanced
7	Asks "who" and "why" questions	3.40	Advanced
8	Gives account of recent experiences (with prompting) in order of occurrence using past tense	2.80	Proficient
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.25	Advanced

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50- 3.24- Proficient ;1.75 – 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 – 1.74– Beginning

Table 11 indicates that teachers perceive learners as advanced in items 4, 6, and 7, while items 1, 2, 3, 5, and 8 are viewed as proficient. This suggests that children can communicate and understand essential daily vocabulary, which is vital for early childhood development. Effective communication helps children express ideas and emotions, fostering relationships and learning. Without strong language skills, children may struggle to engage with their environment, impacting their social interactions and cognitive growth.

Constantino-Lane (2021) highlights that developing communication skills in kindergarten learners is vital for their growth and success, as these skills are essential for social development, literacy, and problem-solving. Without strong communication abilities, children may face challenges in forming relationships and understanding concepts, negatively affecting their academic performance and self-confidence. Therefore, fostering communication skills from an early age is crucial.

Summary on the Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners

Table 12 presents the summary on the level of language skills of the kindergarten learners on receptive and expressive language employed by parents and teachers.

Table 12. Summary on the Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners

Components	Parents		Teachers	
	WM	Verbal Description	WM	Verbal Description
Receptive Language	3.20	Proficient	3.52	Advanced
Expressive Language	3.24	Proficient	3.25	Advanced
Grand Mean	3.22	Proficient	3.39	Advanced

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50- 3.24- Proficient ;1.75 – 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 – 1.74– Beginning

As shown in the table above that the parents' perception on both receptive and expressive language are proficient with weighted mean of 3.22. However, teacher perceived advanced level of language skills of the kindergarten learners with weighted mean of 3.29. This implies that parents and teachers have different opinions on the issue when it comes to assessing children's developmental status, identifying language delays, and deciding whether intervention is necessary. Parents may be more likely to rely on their intuition and have lower expectations of their child's development, while teachers may be more likely to notice any delays and be more aware of the need for intervention. This discrepancy can lead to disagreements about the best approach for the child's development.

According to Zorcic (2020), difference on the perceptions on educating kindergarten learners can create tension between parents and teachers, and can even lead to mistrust between them. It is important for parents and teachers to be open and honest with each other in order to ensure the best outcome for the child. It is also important to remember to be respectful of each other's opinions. Working together in a collaborative manner will help create a positive learning environment for the child. Ultimately, the child's well-being should be the main priority.

Significance of the Difference between the Parents and Teachers' Perceptions on the Language Skills of Kindergarten Learners during the New Normal

Table 13 reflects the test on significant difference between the parents and teachers on the language skills of the kindergarten.

Table 13. Test of Difference between the Parents and Teachers' Perception on the Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners

Source of Difference	Variable	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.	Comp t-value	p-value	Decision	Result
Parents	Receptive	16.00	1.91	-1.60	-1.651	0.114	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	Language	17.60	1.95					
Parents	Expressive	25.89	3.60	-0.11	-0.056	0.953	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	Language	26.00	4.00					

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

The computed mean for parents' assessment of learners' receptive language skills is 16.00 (SD = 1.91), while teachers assessed it at 17.60 (SD = 1.95). For expressive language, parents' mean is 25.89 (SD = 3.60) and teachers' is 26.00 (SD = 4.00). Statistical tests show no significant differences in perceptions: the receptive language mean difference is -1.60 ($t = -1.651$, $p = 0.114$), and the expressive language mean difference is -0.11 ($t = -0.056$, $p = 0.953$). These results suggest that parents and teachers have aligned perceptions of learners' language skills, possibly due to regular contact and shared support efforts.

Khamsuk and Whanchit (2021) suggest that involving both parents and teachers in the assessment of language development is important. It also underlines the need for communication and collaboration between parents and teachers to ensure the learners' language development is accurately assessed. It is also necessary to provide the learners with appropriate resources and support to help them develop their language skills. Furthermore, these results suggest that further research is needed to understand the factors that influence the language development of learners.

Results Of The Data Gathered From King Of Zion Christian Learning Center, Inc.

This section presents the quantitative results related to research questions: Age and Gender of the Parent-Respondents; Highest Educational Attainment of the Parent-Respondents; Parent-Respondents' Number of Children; Parent-Respondents' Combined Family Monthly Income; Age and Gender of the Teacher-Respondents; Teacher-Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment; Length of Service of Teacher-Respondents; Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Receptive Language as perceived by Parents; Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Receptive Language as perceived by Teachers; Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Expressive Language as perceived by Parents; Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Expressive Language as perceived by Teachers; Summary on the Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners and Test of Difference between the Parents and Teachers' Perception on the Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners.

Profile Of The Respondents

This section presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, parents' highest educational attainment, and combined family monthly income.

Parent-Respondents' Age and Gender

As shown in Table 14, there were 24 out of 29 female parents, which comprised 82.76 percent of the respondents, while 5 or 17.24 percent of them were male parents. Twelve, or 41.38 percent, of the female parents were 30-39 years old, followed by six, or 20.69 percent of them, who were 20-29 years old. Furthermore, four, or 13.79 percent, were aged 40-49, and one, or 3.45 percent, was aged 50-59 and older.

Results revealed that majority of the parents' age are under 30-39 years old. This could be due to the fact that parents in this age group are most likely to be in their prime and have more resources and time to invest in their children's education. Additionally, they may be more familiar with the current trends in education and technology, making them better able to support their children's academic success.

Table 14. *Age and Gender of Parent-Respondents*

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Above 59	1	3.45	0	0.00	1	3.45
50-59	1	3.45	2	6.90	3	10.34
40-49	4	13.79	2	6.90	6	20.69
30-39	12	41.38	1	3.45	13	44.83
20-29	6	20.69	0	0.00	6	20.69
Total	24	82.76	5	17.24	29	100.00

According to Nafissi and Shafiee (2020), increased access to education and information might be influencing parents to make more informed decisions about when to start a family, potentially leading to a higher number of parents in their 30s.

Parent-Respondents' Highest educational Attainment

It is believed that parents' educational backgrounds are crucial factors that must be examined in this study to determine the outcomes. The collected data are summarized in Table 15.

Table 15. *Highest Educational Attainment of the Parent-Respondents*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
College Graduate	15	51.72
College Level	6	20.69
High School Graduate	8	27.59
Total	29	100.00

This table shows that fifteen respondents, or 51.72 percent, had earned a college degree, while only eight, or 27.59 percent, had finished high school. Furthermore, six of them, or 20.69%, were college-level. Results revealed that majority of the parents of kindergarten are college graduate. This is likely due to the fact that college-educated parents are better equipped to provide their children with the necessary resources and support to help them excel in school. Additionally, college-educated parents often have higher incomes, allowing them to provide their children with more resources, such as tutoring or extracurricular activities.

Apostolou and Stellakis (2020) noted that higher education is often associated with better economic opportunities. College graduates may be more financially stable, which can contribute to their ability to provide for a family, including the costs associated with raising young children. This could contribute to a higher representation of college-educated parents in kindergarten settings.

Parent-Respondents' Number of Children

The number of children raised by parent respondents is regarded as a crucial variable that must be established in order to interpret the findings of this study. The pertinent data are presented in Table 16.

Table 16. *Parent-Respondents' Number of Children*

<i>Number of Children</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
More than 4	1	3.45
3-4	7	24.14
1-2	21	72.41
Total	29	100.00

According to Table 16, 21 of the 29 respondents or 72.41 percent have 1-2 children, 7 or 24.14 percent have 3-4 children, and 1 or 3.45 percent have more than 4 children. Results revealed that majority of the parents of kindergarten learners have only 1-2 children. This could be due to the costs associated with having a large family, such as the cost of childcare and medical expenses. Additionally, parents may be more likely to have fewer children if they are already financially stable.

According to Puccioni et al. (2020), the cost of raising and providing for children, including education, healthcare, and other expenses, is a significant factor. Some parents may choose to have a smaller family size to ensure they can meet the financial needs of their children more comfortably. Parents may prioritize their careers and work-life balance, and having fewer children can allow for more flexibility in managing professional and family responsibilities.

Parent-Respondents' Combined Family Monthly Income

A family's socioeconomic status, especially the combined monthly income, has a big impact on how their child develops and experiences school. Within the setting of the COVID-19 pandemic's "new normal," where blended learning and remote learning have taken center stage as the main modes of instruction, family resources have a direct bearing on the learning possibilities and results that children experience. The development of language skills in kindergarten students, both receptive and expressive, necessitates regular

assistance and access to educational resources, which may vary depending on the family's socioeconomic situation.

Table 17. *Parent-Respondents' Combined Family*

Monthly Income

<i>Monthly Income (in pesos)</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Above 30,000	11	37.93
25,001-30,000	5	17.24
20,001-25,000	1	3.45
15,001-20,000	5	17.24
10,001-15,000	4	13.79
10,000 and below	3	10.34
Total	29	100.00

Table 17 shows that 11 of the 29 respondents, or 37.93%, had a combined family monthly income of more than 30,000 pesos. Both 5 or 17.24 percent had a monthly family income of between 25,001 and 30,001 and between 15,001 and 20,001. 3 or 10.34 percent had a combined family income of 10,000 and below. In addition, one person, or 3.42 percent, has between 20,001 and 25,500 pesos. Results revealed that majority of the parents of kindergarten learners are earning 25,000 to 30,000 pesos. This can be attributed that majority of the parents are college graduate and working. This is consistent with previous findings that parents with higher incomes are more likely to invest in their children's education. Higher incomes also provide parents with greater access to resources and materials that can help their children succeed in the classroom.

According to Umansky and Dumont (2021), the financial situation can impact a family's access to resources such as extracurricular activities, educational materials, and opportunities for their kindergarten learners. Parents in this income range may need to balance work responsibilities with family needs. This could influence decisions about work hours, job flexibility, and the availability of parents for their children.

Teacher-Respondents' Age and Gender

Table 18. *Teacher-Respondents' Age and Gender*

<i>Age (in years)</i>	<i>Female</i>		<i>Male</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
40-49	1	12.50	0	0.00	1	12.50
30-39	3	37.50	0	0.00	3	37.50
20-29	4	50.00	0	0.00	4	50.00
Total	8	100.00	0	0.00	8	100.00

As shown in Table 18, 8 out of 8 teacher-respondents are female. In their age, it shows that four or 50.00 percent was 20-29 years old and the other three or 37.50 percent was 30-39 years old and one or 12.50% are 40-49 years old. Results revealed that majority of the teachers are 20-29 or in the mid-age and mid-career. This could be due to the fact that teachers at this age have more experience in the classroom and are more confident in their teaching abilities. They may also have more access to resources and support to help them become better educators.

According to Vaiopoulou et al. (2021), many individuals choose to pursue a career in teaching in their early to mid-20s. After completing their education degrees and obtaining teaching certifications, they enter the workforce as new teachers. The age distribution of teachers can also be influenced by the overall workforce dynamics in education. Retirement rates, turnover, and recruitment efforts can contribute to the age profile of teachers in a given period.

Teacher-Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment

The table below is all about the highest educational attainment of the teachers from King of Zion Christian Learning Center, Inc.

Table 19. *Teacher-Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
With Master's Units	5	62.50
Bachelor's Degree	3	37.50
Total	8	100.00

Table 19 shows the Educational Attainment of the three teacher-respondents. In which five or 62.50 percent of them were With Master's Units and three or 37.50 percent were Bachelor's Degree. Results revealed that majority of the respondents have units in master's degree. This indicates that they are highly educated and qualified to teach kindergarteners. The master's degree gives them the knowledge and qualifications to be able to properly teach kindergarteners and help them develop academically.

In the study of Schriever (2021), many educators pursue additional education beyond a bachelor's degree as part of their professional development. Completing units in a master's degree program can enhance a teacher's knowledge and skills, making them more effective

in the classroom.

Teacher-Respondents' Length of Service

The length of service of the teacher respondents is seen to be a crucial element that must be determined for this study in order to explain the findings. The data gathered are presented in Table 20.

Table 20. Teacher-Respondents' Length of Service

<i>Length of Service (in years)</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
6-10	3	37.50
1-5	5	62.50
Total	8	100.00

As shown in Table 20, five or 62.50 percent of the respondents has 1-5 years of teaching and three or 37.50 percent has 6-10 years of teaching. Results revealed that majority of the teachers have 1-5 teaching experience or in the stage of starting their career as teachers. This could be explained by the fact that most teachers enter the profession after obtaining their degree and may not have had the time to gain many years of experience. Additionally, many teachers choose to pursue a career in teaching after already having a few years of experience in the field.

According to Bartolome et al. (2020), there may be a significant number of teachers reaching retirement age. As experienced teachers retire, newer educators enter the profession, contributing to a higher concentration of early-career teachers. Teachers in the early stages of their careers may be more actively engaged in professional development opportunities, seeking to enhance their skills and adapt to the evolving demands of education.

Level Of Language Skills Of The Kindergarten Learners As Perceived By The Parents And Teachers During The New Normal Receptive Language

In assessing language to the learners, parents used a variety of indicators which described above. The table below contains information about the aforementioned indicators.

Table 21. Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Receptive Language as perceived by Parents

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1	Points to family member when asked to do so	3.72	Advanced
2	Points to 5 body parts on himself when asked to do so	3.83	Advanced
3	Points to 5 named pictured objects when asked to do so	3.69	Advanced
4	Follows one-step instructions that include simple prepositions (e.g., in, on, under, etc.)	3.45	Advanced
5	Follows 2-step instructions that include simple prepositions	3.48	Advanced
<i>Aggregate Weighted Mean</i>		3.63	Advanced

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50- 3.24- Proficient ;1.75 – 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 – 1.74– Beginning

Table 21 shows that parents employed advanced level of indicators in teaching language skills as to receptive language to their children in almost all of the items. These indicators focus on how parents spend time with their children in talking and giving simple instruction at home and less exposure to gadgets.

Furthermore, these indicators show on how parents can assist their children in developing the best listening skills and the way they understand instructions. For there is a strong connection between family engagement in a variety of school activities, such as supporting academic success, helping with homework at home, volunteering in schools, and taking part in governance activities, and the advantages that education brings to children regardless of their socioeconomic, racial/ethnic, or educational backgrounds.

Family engagement in school activities has been shown to improve student attendance, behavior, and academic performance. It can also enhance parent-child relationships, increase student motivation and self-esteem, and foster a supportive learning environment. Additionally, when families are actively involved in schools, it promotes a positive school climate, builds a sense of community, and strengthens the partnership between home and school.

According to Lampis et al. (2023), parents assist their children in developing the best listening skills and the way they understand instructions by setting expectations and reinforcing them through positive reinforcement. They can also model good listening skills for their children and provide feedback on how they can improve their listening. Additionally, they can provide their children with opportunities to practice and develop their listening skills, such as by engaging in activities that involve active listening. Parents should also reward their children when they demonstrate good listening skills. They should also focus on building an environment of trust and open communication, which will encourage their children to share their thoughts and feelings.

Table 22 is all about the level of language skills of the kindergarten learners as to Receptive Language as perceived by Teachers from King of Zion Christian Learning Center, Inc. This shows that teachers employed proficient level indicators as to receptive language in almost all the items except number 1 and 3. Most of those indicators show that learners can follow steps and instructions when asked to do so.

Table 22. *Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Receptive Language as perceived by Teachers*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Points to family member when asked to do so	3.25	Advanced
2	Points to 5 body parts on himself when asked to do so	3.00	Proficient
3	Points to 5 named pictured objects when asked to do so	3.25	Advanced
4	Follows one-step instructions that include simple prepositions (e.g., in,on,under.etc.)	2.75	Proficient
5	Follows 2-step instructions that include simple prepositions	2.75	Proficient
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.00	Proficient

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50- 3.24- Proficient ;1.75 – 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 – 1.74– Beginning

Moreover, they can understand language concept. Strong receptive language skills of the learners are essential to allow them to complete the tasks, participate in class, understand and follow rules in the classroom.

According to Mazlan et al. (2022), without strong receptive language skills, the learners cannot understand the instructions given to them, which can lead to confusion and disruptions in the classroom. It can also hinder the learners' ability to complete tasks and participate in class discussions.

Expressive Language

This section discusses how parents may use sample indicators to examine their children's expressive language. The table summarizes the expressive language skills of kindergarten pupils at King of Zion Christian Learning Center, Inc. as perceived by their parents.

Table 23. *Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Expressive Language as perceived by Parents*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Uses 5-20 recognizable words	3.45	Advanced
2	Uses pronouns (e.g. I, me, ako, akin)	3.41	Advanced
3	Uses 2-3 words verb-noun combinations(e.g. hingi gatas)	3.41	Advanced
4	Names objects in pictures	3.72	Advanced
5	Speaks in grammatically correct 2-3 word sentences	3.17	Proficient
6	Asks "what" questions	3.66	Advanced
7	Asks "who" 'and "why" questions	3.69	Advanced
8	Gives account of recent experiences (with prompting) in order of occurrence using past tense	3.17	Proficient
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.46	Advanced

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50- 3.24- Proficient ;1.75 – 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 – 1.74– Beginning

Table 23 demonstrates that, with the exception of items 5 and 8, parents used advanced level language abilities of kindergarten learners for expressive language in all items.

As shown on the table, that mostly children can ask WH-questions, name objects in a picture, use recognizable words and verb-noun combinations. They can express themselves more clearly and correctly using proper words. Moreover, they can also talk about their day and have basic conversations with their parents.

Parents can engage their children in conversations by asking open-ended questions that require more than a simple "yes" or "no" response. They can also encourage children to talk about their daily activities and emotions by actively listening and asking follow-up questions. Additionally, parents can use descriptive language when speaking to their children, using adjectives and adverbs to expand on their vocabulary and promote more complex conversations.

According to Aladsani et al. (2022), that there is no doubt that parents are good influences on children because they receive the assistance and support they need from them. A positive parental influence on a child's communication style can have a significant impact on their ability to communicate with others. Good parenting skills can help children develop strong communication and language skills. This can be done by encouraging their children to express themselves, providing a safe and nurturing environment, and modelling positive communication behaviour.

Table 24. *Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Expressive Language as perceived by Teachers*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Uses 5-20 recognizable words	3.00	Proficient
2	Uses pronouns (e.g. I, me, ako, akin)	2.75	Proficient
3	Uses 2-3 words verb-noun combinations(e.g. hingi gatas)	3.00	Proficient
4	Names objects in pictures	3.13	Proficient
5	Speaks in grammatically correct 2-3 word sentences	2.50	Proficient
6	Asks "what" questions	3.25	Advanced
7	Asks "who" 'and "why" questions	3.13	Proficient
8	Gives account of recent experiences (with prompting)in order of occurrence using past tense	2.63	Proficient
Aggregate Weighted Mean		2.92	Proficient

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50- 3.24- Proficient ;1.75 – 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 – 1.74– Beginning

As shown on the table 24, it reveals that teachers perceived a proficient level on all items except item number 6. This means that to help kindergarten learners improve their expressive language, and teachers should plan more exciting and fun activities based on their age and level of language. A child will express themselves using words and phrases. Teachers often use learners' expressive language to determine if they need more help. It can reveal a child's level of development and whether they have any skill deficiencies. According to their teachers, the kindergarten learners at King of Zion Christian Learning Center, Inc. have the following expressive language skills, summarized in the table above.

Teachers play a crucial role in supporting and improving learners' expressive language skills. Through observation and assessment of learners' expressive language, teachers can identify areas where additional support and intervention are needed. They provide individualized instruction, modeling correct usage and encouraging learners to express themselves more fluently and confidently. Additionally, teachers create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment where learners feel comfortable using language, fostering meaningful interactions and enhancing their overall language development.

According to Komesidou et al. (2022), children can improve their ability to express themselves via play by participating in engaging practice activities. Pretending or making up stories helps kids hone their narrative and sequence of events skills, which in turn helps them express themselves more fully in speech.

Summary on the Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners

Table 25. Summary on the Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners

Components	Parents		Teachers	
	WM	Verbal Description	WM	Verbal Description
Receptive Language	3.63	Advanced	3.00	Proficient
Expressive Language	3.46	Advanced	2.92	Proficient
Grand Mean	3.55	Advanced	2.96	Proficient

The table 25 summarizes the kindergarten students' language proficiency in the receptive and expressive languages used by parents and teachers. As shown in the table above that the parents' perception on both receptive and expressive language are advanced with weighted mean of 3.55. However, teachers perceived proficient level of language skills of the kindergarten learners with weighted mean of 2.96.

This means that parents and teachers have different ideas about how to judge a child's development, spot language delays, and decide if they need help. Parents often rely on their feelings and intuition to identify a problem, while teachers use structured assessments and observations to evaluate a child's development. Both approaches are valid, but it is important that parents and teachers work together to ensure the best outcome for the child.

According to Stillerova et al. (2021), teachers are more concerned with the student's academic achievement and better able to identify learning difficulties, but parents often have a more intimate relationship with the kid and are more inclined to detect subtle changes in behavior and ability. Teachers can see when a student is struggling, but parents can fill in the gaps in knowledge that teachers lack, allowing them to provide their children the best possible care.

Significance Of The Difference Between The Parents And Teachers' Perception On The Language Skills Of Kindergarten Learners During The New Normal

Table 26. Test of Difference between the Parents and Teachers' Perception on the Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners

Source of Difference	Variable	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.	Comp t-value	p-value	Decision	Result
Parents	Receptive Language	18.17	1.54	3.17	5.458*	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Teachers		15.00	1.07					
Parents	Expressive Language	27.69	3.17	4.31	3.508*	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Teachers		23.38	2.67					

*significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 26 above shows the significant difference between the parents and teachers in the language skills of the kindergarten. The calculated mean of learners' receptive language skills, as reported by their parents, is 18.17, with a standard deviation of 1.54. In contrast, the teachers' computed mean is 15.00 with a 1.07 standard deviation. Furthermore, the calculated mean for the parents' expressive language skills toward learners is 27.69 with a 3.17 standard deviation, while the mean for the expressive language skills toward learners encountered by the teachers is 23.38 with a 2.67 standard deviation. The mean difference for the receptive language shown is 3.17, with a computed t-value of 5.458* and a p-value of 0.000, less than 0.05. So, the null hypothesis can be thrown out because there is a significant link between the two variables.

On the other hand, the mean difference for the expressive language showed is 4.31 with a computed t-value of 3.508 and a p-value of 0.001, which is less than 0.05, suggesting that the null hypothesis is rejected because there is a significant difference between the two

variables.

The results indicate a significant difference between the parents' and teachers' perceptions of the learners' language skills, particularly receptive and expressive language. The discrepancy in perceptions could be due to various factors. Parents may have a more subjective view of the learners' language skills, as they often observe them in a home environment. Teachers, on the other hand, have a more comprehensive view based on consistent observations and assessments in a controlled educational setting. Additionally, different teaching methodologies and assessment practices employed by teachers and parents may also contribute to the variation in perceptions.

In the study of Dermitzaki and Kallia (2021), teachers reported higher scores on receptive and expressive language than parents. This suggests that parents may not be accurately assessing their children's language skills. Further research is needed to explore this discrepancy.

Results From The Two Identified Schools

This section presents the combined findings from two identified public and private schools in Magsaysay Elementary School, Sevilla District, Bohol Division and King of Zion Christian Learning Center, Inc., Yati, Liloan, Cebu Division that sought to assess the language skills of the kindergarten learners during new normal on the respondents' profile, the level of language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Receptive Language, the level of language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Expressive Language, and significant difference between parents' and teachers' perception on the language skills of the kindergarten learners during new normal.

Parent-Respondents' Age and Gender

The 27 respondents from Magsaysay Elementary School and King of Zion Christian Learning Center, Inc. are all listed in the table below by their age and gender.

Table 27. *Age and Gender of Parent-Respondents*

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Above 59	1	2.13	0	0.00	1	2.13
50-59	2	4.26	2	4.26	4	8.51
40-49	11	23.40	3	6.38	14	29.79
30-39	17	36.17	1	2.13	18	38.30
20-29	10	21.28	0	0.00	10	21.28
Total	41	87.23	6	12.77	47	100.00

Table 27 shows the age and gender of the parents. It shows that, in their age, 18 or 38.30% are 30-39 years old, 14 or 29.79% are 40-49 years old, 10 or 21.28% are 20-29 years old, 4 or 8.51 % are 50-59 years old and 1 or 2.13% are above 59 years old. In their gender, 41 or 87.23% are female and 6 or 12.77% are male.

Results revealed that majority of the parents of the kindergarten learners are 30-39 years old and female. There may be a trend where couples or individuals choose to start their families in their 30s. This could be influenced by factors such as career stability, financial readiness, and personal preferences. Individuals, particularly women, may choose to delay parenthood to pursue personal goals, such as education, career advancement, or other life aspirations. This decision may result in a higher percentage of parents in the specified age range.

According to Ogg et al. (2021), the period between birth and the age of three is pivotal for language development due to the brain's fast growth and development throughout this time. Parents with lower levels of education may not realize the need of talking to their newborns on a regular basis, which might delay the onset of language skills in their children.

Parents-Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment

The table below is all about the highest educational attainment of the parents of the learners.

Table 28. *Parent-Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
College Graduate	15	31.91
College Level	7	14.89
High School Graduate	14	29.79
High School Level	3	6.38
Elementary Graduate	5	10.64
Elementary Level	3	6.38
Total	47	100.00

Table 28 shows the highest educational attainment of the parents of the learners. It shows that 15 or 31.91% are college graduate, 14 or 29.79% are high school graduate, 7 or 14.89% are college level, 5 or 10.64 are elementary graduate, 3 or 6.38% are both high school level and elementary level.

Results revealed that majority of the learners' parents are college graduate. Parents who are college graduates may place a high value on education and aspire for their children to attain similar educational achievements. This can result in a higher percentage of college-educated parents among learners. College education is often associated with higher socioeconomic status. Families with higher levels of education may have greater access to resources, including educational opportunities, which can positively impact their children's academic outcomes.

According to Kanwal and Muhammad (2022), all parents have power, and their expertise and experience can be extremely beneficial to their children's learning processes. In addition to being a child's first teacher, parents play a crucial role in the development of their language and reading skills. This indicates that if the parents of a student have a high level of education, the student is likely to have a high degree of responsiveness to stimuli and comprehension as well.

Parent-Respondents' Number of Children

Table 29 lists the parents' total number of children. It shows that 28 or 59.57% have 1-2 number of children, 12 or 25.53% have 3-4 children and 7 or 14.89% have more than 4 number of children.

Table 29. *Parent-Respondents' Number of Children*

<i>Number of Children</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
More than 4	7	14.89
3-4	12	25.53
1-2	28	59.57
Total	47	100.00

As a result, the majority of parents of the kindergarten learners have 1-2 children. Some parents may actively choose to have a smaller family size based on their family planning preferences. Personal decisions regarding the desired number of children can contribute to a higher percentage of families with 1-2 children.

According to Louie et al. (2021), parents who prioritize their careers or have specific lifestyle preferences may opt for a smaller family size. Balancing work and family responsibilities can be more manageable with fewer children.

Combined Family Monthly Income

The combined family income in Philippine Peso is shown in the table below. The income range, frequency, and percentage are listed for each category

Table 30. *Parent-Respondents' Combined Family Monthly Income*

<i>Monthly Income (in pesos)</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Above 30,000	11	23.40
25,001-30,000	5	10.64
20,001-25,000	1	2.13
15,001-20,000	6	12.77
10,001-15,000	5	10.64
10,000 and below	19	40.43
Total	47	100.00

Table 30 shows the combined family monthly income of the parents of the learners. It shows that 1 or 2.13% earn above 20,001-25,000, 5 or 10.64% earn 25,001-30,000 pesos and 10,001-15,000, 6 or 12.77% earn 15,001-20,000 pesos, 11 or 23.40% earn above 30,000 pesos, 19 or 40.43% earn 10,000 and below pesos.

Therefore, majority of the parents of the kindergarten learners have a combined family monthly income of 10,000 pesos and below. Factors can interact in complex ways, and the specific reasons for the observed income distribution would depend on the context of the community or region in question. Analyzing more detailed data about the local economy, employment opportunities, and social support structures would provide a clearer understanding of the dynamics contributing to the majority of parents having a combined family monthly income of 10,000 pesos and below.

According to Ng et al. (2020), a family's total monthly income might change drastically based on variables including the number of breadwinners, their jobs, education level, geographic region, and general economic climate. Income levels can vary greatly from one home to another, falling anywhere from the lowest to the highest tiers. A family's capacity to pay for necessities like housing, food, healthcare, education, transportation, and other financial commitments is heavily dependent on the total monthly income of all family members.

Teacher-Respondents, Age and Gender

Age and gender of the teacher-respondents are considered to be important factors that must be established in this study and may aid in explaining the outcome. Table 31 displays the data gathered from the two identified schools.

Table 31. *Age and Gender of the Teacher-Respondents*

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
40-49	4	30.77	0	0.00	4	30.77
30-39	5	38.46	0	0.00	5	38.46
20-29	4	30.77	0	0.00	4	30.77
Total	13	100.00	0	0.00	13	100.00

As shown in Table 31, all the teachers are female. There are five out of thirteen or 38.46 percent teacher-respondents are at the age range of 30-39. Both 5 or 30.77 percent are 40-49 years old and 20-29.

Based on the teachers' ages, shown in the table, they are still early in their careers and want to find effective ways to teach language skills that will meet the needs of the learners.

According to Chen et al. (2021), the 30-39 age range represents a stage in the career progression of teachers. Many teachers in this age group may have advanced from entry-level positions to more experienced roles, taking on responsibilities such as mentorship, curriculum development, or leadership within the school or district.

Teacher-Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment

The educational level of the two chosen schools is presented in this part since it is thought to be an important factor that must be discovered for this study in order to explain the findings. The statistics gathered are presented in Table 32.

Table 32. *Teacher-Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Master's Graduate	1	7.69
With Master's Units	9	69.23
Bachelor's Degree	3	23.08
Total	13	100.00

As shown in table 32, 9 out of 13 or 69.23 percent earned master's units and three or 23.08 percent had their bachelor's degree. 1 or 7.69 percent is a master graduate.

Most educators put in a lot of effort to finish their master's degrees. They take classes, work on assignments, and juggle other responsibilities. All this hard work pays off in the end as they gain new knowledge and skills that can help them in their careers.

Furthermore, a master's degree gives teachers a highly technical understanding of their chosen field. Additionally, this degree can enhance a teacher's instructional abilities, leading to improved standard exam scores and increased graduation rates.

According to Steed and Leech (2021), most early childhood teachers put in a lot of effort to finish their master's degrees nowadays. The process is challenging but rewarding. It helps them to become more knowledgeable in their field and gain new skills. This is beneficial for their students, as they can provide better teaching and support. The new skills they acquire can help them create more engaging lesson plans and be better able to identify and address the needs of their students. They also gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter, which can help them to better explain concepts and provide students with more effective resources

Teacher-Respondents' Length of Service

The length of service of the teacher of the two identified schools are shown in Table 33.

Table 33. *Teacher-Respondents Length of Service*

<i>Length of Service (in years)</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
16 and above	3	23.08
11-15	0	0.00
6-10	4	30.77
1-5	6	46.15
Total	13	100.00

As presented in table 33, out of thirteen teachers, six or 46.15 percent already lent 1-5 years of service followed by four or 30.77 percent already stayed for 6-10 years. Additionally, zero percent lent 11-15 years of service.

Based on the years they spent working as teachers, they have a lot of strategies for teaching the young learners to express and understand language. As teachers, they have experienced firsthand the challenges of teaching language to students, and they have developed effective and efficient strategies for helping them learn. This includes methods such as providing visual aids, repetition, and positive reinforcement.

In the study of Su et al. (2022), the length of service in kindergarten teaching can also impact a teacher's ability to build relationships with students, parents, and colleagues. Over time, experienced kindergarten teachers may develop strong connections with the families they serve and establish a reputation for their expertise in early childhood education.

Level Of Language Skills Of The Kindergarten Learners As Perceived By The Parents And Teachers During The New Normal

Receptive Language

Table 34. *Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Receptive Language as perceived by Parents*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Points to family member when asked to do so	3.51	Advanced
2	Points to 5 body parts on himself when asked to do so	3.62	Advanced
3	Points to 5 named pictured objects when asked to do so	3.49	Advanced
4	Follows one-step instructions that include simple prepositions (e.g., in,on,under,etc.)	3.38	Advanced
5	Follows 2-step instructions that include simple prepositions	3.34	Advanced
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.47	Advanced

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50- 3.24- Proficient ;1.75 – 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 – 1.74– Beginning

The table above details the level of receptive language proficiency of kindergarten learners as perceived by parents in two schools. It reveals that the parents' insight with regards with the receptive language of the kindergarten is advanced level. This means that the learners can able to response positively and comprehensively. They learn to listen, react and follow directions with their own instinct.

This implies that the parents have a good understanding of the importance of receptive language in early childhood development. By being proactive in the development of their children's receptive language skills, parents can help their children to develop successful communication and literacy skills.

According to Chavez et al. (2023), learners learn to recognize objects in books when they hear their parents or guardians call out the name of an object or point out the right color while reading or playing, which is just one of hundreds of everyday interactions with adults. The inverse is also true: when a kid is slow to pick up on fundamental receptive language abilities, it can cause them to fall behind in other areas of development and even hinder their ability to pick up spoken language in the future. Students learn hundreds of different receptive language objectives after several early intensive behavioral intervention programs teach them to respond to their name or basic instructions.

Table 35. *Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Receptive Language as perceived by Teachers*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Points to family member when asked to do so	3.38	Advanced
2	Points to 5 body parts on himself when asked to do so	3.31	Advanced
3	Points to 5 named pictured objects when asked to do so	3.38	Advanced
4	Follows one-step instructions that include simple prepositions (e.g., in,on,under,etc.)	3.00	Proficient
5	Follows 2-step instructions that include simple prepositions	2.92	Proficient
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.20	Proficient

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50- 3.24- Proficient ;1.75 – 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 – 1.74– Beginning

Table 35 shows that the teachers employed advanced level of language skills to the learners as to receptive language except item number 5. It means that the learners can respond quickly to the teachers' instructions. This helps to keep the classroom organized and helps to ensure that classes run smoothly. Additionally, it helps to foster a sense of respect and discipline among students. The advanced language skills required of the teachers enables them to be understood clearly by the students, and to be able to explain complex concepts in simple terms. This helps to ensure that students are able to comprehend the instructions quickly and correctly, and that they are able to respond in a timely manner. It also helps to create a positive learning environment by showing the students that their teachers respect them and value their input.

According to Egan et al. (2021), young toddlers acquire language comprehension rapidly as they get accustomed to their names and familiar voices, obey basic directions, and comprehend a variety of environmental cues and events. When stimuli are learned through repetition, they are better recalled and kept for longer periods of time. Research indicates that when a task is repeated, the brain frequently builds new neural connections, therefore enhancing skill performance.

Expressive Language

Table 36 shows that parents perceived an advanced level except for the item number 5 and 8. Parent-child interactions have a great impact of the language development of the learners. Early interactions between parents and their children lay the groundwork for future learning skills. These interactions can take place through play, reading, and conversations.

Table 36. *Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Expressive Language as perceived by Parents*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Uses 5-20 recognizable words	3.34	Advanced
2	Uses pronouns (e.g. I, me, ako, akin)	3.40	Advanced
3	Uses 2-3 words verb-noun combinations(e.g. hingi gatas)	3.36	Advanced
4	Names objects in pictures	3.55	Advanced
5	Speaks in grammatically correct 2-3 word sentences	3.13	Proficient
6	Asks “what” questions	3.53	Advanced
7	Asks “who” and “why” questions	3.49	Advanced
8	Gives account of recent experiences (with prompting) in order of occurrence using past tense	3.19	Proficient
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.38	Advanced

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50-3.24- Proficient ;1.75 – 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 – 1.74– Beginning

When children interact with their parents, they are exposed to more language and will learn more words. This is because parents use more complex language and are more patient when interacting with their children, which helps them to learn more quickly. Additionally, when parents interact with their children, they provide a more supportive learning environment. This encourages children to be more engaged in the learning process, which further accelerates their language development.

According to Wallace and Leong (2020), reading aloud to youngsters and introducing them to new vocabulary terms are two ways parents support their children's language development. This aids kids in learning new words and using them appropriately. Their vocabulary will grow and they will be inspired to use language in more sophisticated ways because of this. They are also encouraged to ask questions and provide suitable answers, which helps to build their critical thinking abilities.

Table 37. *Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners as to Expressive Language as perceived by Teachers*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Uses 5-20 recognizable words	2.92	Proficient
2	Uses pronouns (e.g. I, me, ako, akin)	2.92	Proficient
3	Uses 2-3 words verb-noun combinations(e.g. hingi gatas)	3.08	Proficient
4	Names objects in pictures	3.38	Advanced
5	Speaks in grammatically correct 2-3 word sentences	2.69	Proficient
6	Asks “what” questions	3.46	Advanced
7	Asks “who” and “why” questions	3.23	Proficient
8	Gives account of recent experiences (with prompting)in order of occurrence using past tense	2.69	Proficient
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.05	Proficient

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Advanced; 2.50-3.24- Proficient ;1.75 – 2.49-Developing ; 1.00 – 1.74– Beginning

As shown on the table above, it reveals that teachers perceived a proficient level on all items except item number 4 & 6. This implies that a learner's language proficiency can vary from class to class depending on the type of task and the learning context. Providing a non-judgmental environment for learners' expressive skills is critical, as they are prone to be mocked by peers. Results highlight the importance of providing a supportive learning environment for learners, so that they can feel comfortable taking risks and exploring their language. If learners feel judged or laughed at, they may be reluctant to express certain ideas, which can lead to them becoming discouraged and not developing their skills to the fullest.

According to Haatainen and Aksela (2021), numerous language teachers employ communicative activities in order to foster language learners' communicative ability. Atmosphere and classroom environment are critical for successful instruction and learning. These are valued greatly by the kids. In order to maintain their students' attention, educators engage them in a variety of speaking and writing exercises. It is necessary to establish a lesson plan and term syllabus in advance of each teaching period. An effective educator discerns what is most beneficial for each pupil.

Summary on the Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners

Table 38. *Summary on the Level of Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners*

Components	Parents		Teachers	
	WM	Verbal Description	WM	Verbal Description
Receptive Language	3.47	Advanced	3.20	Proficient
Expressive Language	3.38	Advanced	3.05	Proficient
Grand Mean	3.43	Advanced	3.13	Proficient

The table implies the summary on the level of language skills of the kindergarten learners on receptive and expressive language employed by parents and teachers in two schools. As shown in the table above that the parents' perception on both receptive and expressive language are advanced with weighted mean of 3.43. However, teacher perceived proficient level of language skills of the kindergarten learners with weighted mean of 3.13.

This is because parents tend to have higher expectations for their children's language development and are more aware of the importance of language in development. They are likely to be more engaged with their children when it comes to language development and may have more knowledge on language development compared to other adults.

According to Gross et al. (2020), parents tend to have a better understanding of their children's language development than professionals or other adults. This is due to the fact that parents are with their children more often and can observe their language development as it progresses.

Significance Of The Difference Between Parents And Teachers Of Magsaysay Elementary And King Of Zion Christian Learning Center Inc. On Language Skills Of The Kindergarten Learners During The New Normal

This section presents the difference between strategies in teaching reading which is presented in Table 39. This table reflects the test on significant difference between the parents and teachers' perception on the language skills of the kindergarten learners in Magsaysay Elementary School and King of Zion Christian Learning Center, Inc.

Table 39. *Test of Difference between the Parents and Teachers' Perception on the Language Skills of the Kindergarten Learners*

Source of Difference	Variable	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.	Comp t-value	p-value	Decision	Result
Parents	Receptive Language	17.34	1.98	1.34	2.174*	0.034	Reject Ho	Significant
Teachers		16.00	1.91					
Parents	Expressive Language	27.00	3.42	2.62	2.450*	0.017	Reject Ho	Significant
Teachers		24.38	3.36					

*significant at $p < 0.05$

The calculated mean of learners' receptive language skills, as reported by their parents, is 17.34, with a standard deviation of 1.98. In contrast, the teachers' computed mean is 16.00 with a 1.91 standard deviation. Furthermore, the calculated mean for the parents' expressive language skills toward learners is 27.00 with a 3.42 standard deviation, while the mean for the expressive language skills toward learners encountered by the teachers is 24.38 with a 3.36 standard deviation. The mean difference for the receptive language shown is 1.34, with a computed t-value of 2.174* and a p-value of 0.034 greater than 0.05. So, the null hypothesis can be thrown out because there is a significant link between the two variables.

On the other hand, the mean difference for the expressive language showed is 2.62 with a computed t-value of 24.50 and a p-value of 0.017, which is greater than 0.05, suggesting that the null hypothesis is rejected because there is a significant difference between the two variables. The results indicate a significant difference between the parents' and teachers' perceptions of the learners' language skills, particularly receptive and expressive language.

According to Kaynar et al. (2020), teachers and parents evaluate the child's language proficiency in a variety of settings. Teachers monitor a child's language talents in a regulated school environment, whereas parents primarily observe their child's language abilities at home. There may be variations in the child's language proficiency and conduct across these situations, which may result in contrasting views.

Conclusions

After analyzing the data, it was observed that the language skills of the learners are at an advanced level based on the observation of the parents, indicating strong agreement with the learners' proficiency in the language skills assessed. This suggests a high level of comprehension and expression, with learners effectively communicating their thoughts and ideas. This advanced level was influenced by certain factors, highlighting the importance of parental involvement in fostering language development. Parents should continue to provide time and effort to explore and socialize their children, engaging them in activities that improve listening and speaking skills, such as storytelling and open-ended questions. They should also involve learners in different vocabulary activities and provide them with background knowledge to further enhance their language abilities.

In contrast, the teachers perceived the language skills of the kindergarten learners as proficient, suggesting agreement with the learners' proficiency in the language skills assessed. This indicates that the learners demonstrate a good understanding of the language and are able to communicate effectively in various contexts. To further enhance these skills, teachers should provide more engaging and interesting language activities that hone their interest and motivation in expressing themselves and understanding various scenarios. By focusing on these aspects and working collaboratively, both parents and teachers can significantly boost the language skills of learners, ensuring a well-rounded and comprehensive approach to language development.

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